

Fullerene-DBP conjugates : Their co-occurrence in meteorites, ammonites and Shilajit, and application in systemic drug delivery

Shibnath Ghosal* and Muruganandam A. V.

R & D Centre, Indian Herbs Ltd., Saharanpur-247 001, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : vishnu20024@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 5 August 2008, accepted 12 August 2008

Abstract : A unified manifestation of the macrocosmic and microcosmic actions is expressed by the co-occurrence of C₆₀-fullerene-dibenzo- α -pyrone (DBP) conjugates in meteorites, ammonites, and Shilajit. The crystal forms of mineral (aragonite) deposition in ammonites (the major marine precursors of Shilajit), are distinctly different in many respects from the inorganic mineral, aragonite. The mineral deposition in the living ammonite shells is under strict biological control and involves organo-mineral complexes received from meteorites. These constituents in ammonites are eventually transformed into Shilajit by humification. Hence, the supramolecular assemblies of complex chemical constituents of ammonites, in many respects, show striking similarities with the humic constituents (FAs, HAs and HMs) of meteorites and of Shilajit. Some selected assemblies, viz. fusoms and DCPs, of Shilajit, comprising of fullerene-DBP conjugates in their inner core, were found to confer facile water-solubility, stability and superior bioavailability (*Yogabahi* in Ayurveda) to a host of chemical agents that are ordinarily water-insoluble, thermolabile, autoxidizable, and/or prematurely biodegradable before reaching the target site. The potential of this superior drug delivery system is evaluated.

Keywords : Meteorites, ammonites, Shilajit, fullerene-DBP conjugates, drug delivery.

Introduction

The occurrence of three new categories of cellular energy transducers, namely, (i) oxygenated DBPs and acyl-DBP-metallo-proteins (DCPs); (ii) PBQs and (iii) C₆₀- and other fullerene derivatives, in the interior of four chondrite meteorites of the fall- and find-types has recently been reported¹. The occurrence and purposive aspects of these complex molecules in meteorites have, however, eluded the notice of previous investigators².

Meteoritic debris relentlessly fall to the Earth's surface since the birth of this planet. Everyday, about 10⁵ to 10⁶ kg of such debris fall² on Earth, mostly to the seas. Sea-animals, particularly the molluscs (e.g. Ammonites) absorb and utilize the organo-mineral constituents of the meteorites for constructing their shelled structures and for body-growth, sustenance and for interactions with preys and predators^{3,4}. The nacreous shells of ammonites are composed of the mineral aragonite, proteins (e.g. conchiolins) and organo-mineral constituents of stellar debris. The mineral deposition in ammonite shells is under strict biological control of the living animals. The mantle, a thin tissue which covers the entire animal and adheres

to the shell, as the animal grows, exhibits this control. Each aragonite layer is about the thickness of the average wavelength of visible light. As light enters the shell, it is refracted and reflected like passing through a prism. This photophysical effect is augmented by the interactions of the supramolecular organomineral assemblies (MLVs), present in the ammonite shells; the latter also act as central agents for many biochemical functions of the living animal. Under their influence, the human eye perceives an array of brilliant iridescence and also visible colours. The visible colours are contributed⁵ by the contained carotenoids, indigoids, and the now identified fullerenes. Besides the colour components, some other complex organic conjugates received by the ammonites from the meteorites serve certain essential biological purposes of the animal^{1,5}. The genesis of these essential constituents was eventually taken over by the living system during replication.

A large number and abundance of marine fossil-invertebrates, especially of the Ammonoidea³, are found on top of sedimentary mountains. This happens when the sea floor is raised by the collision of the continents

(plate tectonics) resulting into formation of high mountain ranges, e.g. the grandiose Himalayas. Percolation of rain water then sets the process into reverse when the fossil materials or their chemical constituents appear at different heights of sedimentary rocks of different formations. Following the biotic reactions by rock-soil microorganisms and abiotic transformations involving geochemical and geothermal processes, the rock-rhizospheric organic constituents and minerals are transformed into rock-humus of various complexities^{4,5}. The rich mineral contents of sedimentary rocks act as fixers of humus against leaching by rain or mountain river-water^{5,6}. The slowly transformed organo-mineral products appear as blackish-brown exudation on rock-surface and fissures, which is known as Shilajit^{4,5}. Thus, the genesis of Shilajit, the foremost among the Ayurvedic *rasayan*s (rejuvenators), manifests a harmonic exchange of material bodies among the macro and microcosmic subjects :

The chemistry involved in the above transport and the biological consequences thereof constitute the subject of this paper.

Results and discussion

A general method of extraction of the complex organo-mineral constituents from meteorites, ammonites and Shilajit is depicted in Scheme 1. The three broad categories of compounds, viz. (i) FAs-fusoms; (ii) DCPs and (iii) HMs-HAs, extracted from the meteorites¹, ammonites⁵ and Shilajit⁵, were further processed (Treatment-A, -B and -C, vide Experimental), separately, for isolation and characterization of the compounds contained in (i)-(iii).

FAs-fusoms : The FAs-fusoms, referred here, comprise mono-, di- and oligomeric condensates of 3,8-oxygenated dibenzo- α -pyrones, as the core nuclei, substituted with C- and O- fatty acyl-, aminoacyl, acylsugars, and other simpler phenolic moieties (e.g. hydroxy acetophenones); the combined composition(s) assumes liposomic character, hence the term fusoms. Additionally, within the fusoms, there are cavitand-packed metal ions (Fe, Cu, Zn) with other chemical agents/ligands. The FAs-fusoms fraction, obtained from Scheme 1, on further processing, gave a pinkish-black solid which, on comprehensive chromatographic and spectroscopic analysis, was identified as C₆₀-fullerene-3,8-deoxygenated-DBP endo-exohedral conjugates. Synthesis of the

compound from C₆₀-fullerene-3,8-dioxygenated dibenzo- α -pyrone (DBP) and metal ions established its identity with fullerene-DBP-metal ion C-T complex (L in Str. 1). The fusoms, in aqueous solution, assume supramolecular assembly structures, whose major chemical architecture is depicted in Str. 1. The exohedrally attached DBP-metal ion component was dissociated from the pinkish-black solid by treatment with polar solvents, when the endohedral complex was obtained as a dull-yellow insoluble residue. It exhibited; in the ESR spectrum, very narrow single line, devoid of hyperfine splitting, with a g-value ranging from 1.99–2.001 (for samples resulting from the three parent sources, -meteorites, ammonites and Shilajit). These data suggest the existence of an odd-electron species (e.g. DBP semiquinone radical)⁵. This postulate is further supported by the weak conductivity exhibited by the endohedral complex in the lobar chromatography (Bio-Rad). Such C-T complex formation with fullerene and electron-donating pi-systems has precedent in the literature^{7,8}.

L = ligand; organic compounds, fullerenes

M = Fe, Cu, Mn, Mo, Zn

Str. 1. Fullerene-DBP-endo-/exohedral complex (L) in FAs (fusoms).

Astronomical and astrophysical considerations led to searches for fullerenes in meteorites. Becker *et al.* were the first to have reported the occurrence of (C₆₀)-fullerene in the C3V chondrite meteorite, Allende. Later, these workers reported, that, another meteorite, the Tagish Lake carbonaceous chondrite, that fell in the year 2000 on a frozen lake in Canada, contained a large array of organic compounds, including fullerene derivatives¹⁰. Fullerenes are not native to Earth. They occur as nested nanotubes in interplanetary dust and in meteorites. The organo-mineral constituents of the stellar bodies and the noble gases are trapped within the fullerene nanotubes and transported to Earth. The organic compounds, admixed into meteoritic debris are captured by marine shelled animals (e.g. molluscs). Later, transport of the shelled bodies (carcass, fossils) to sedimentary mountain tops, by plate tectonics, followed by humification and mineralization over hundreds and thousands of years,

Scheme 1. A general method of extraction of complex organic compounds of meteorites¹, ammonites⁵ and Shilajit^{5,6}.

Shilajit is produced⁵. Thus, the organic constituents of meteorites, including the complex fullerene derivatives are transformed into Shilajit humus (HMs, HAs and FAs), via absorption and metabolism by sea-animals, e.g. ammonites. The spheroidal voids, occurring in FAs-fusoms⁵, can completely engulf fullerene-DBP complexes (L in Str. 1) and mask their identities. The complex assembly, thus generated, behaves as a liposome (hence the name fusom) with MLV/SUV character. The stability of such molecular assemblies is due, at least partly, to recognition of the five- and six-fold symmetric structural modification of fullerene¹¹. Additionally, H-bonding by the phenolic DBP-moieties, with fullerene in the complex and

the DBP-metal ion chelation (L in Str. 1) augment the stability of the supramolecular assembly in Shilajit-fusoms.

The crystallinity, shapes, diameter and extent of aggregation of the particles in fusoms depend on the pH of the solution in which they are dissolved^{12,13}. Three types of fusom particles were observed in TEM : (i) small spheroids (2–5 nm in diameter); these are capable of encapsulating the fullerene-DBP complexes; (ii) aggregation of spheroids (20–30 nm in diam.) and (iii) amorphous fusom particles perforated by voids (50–100 nm in diam.). Within the voids of these fusom particles, several complex organic molecules can find suitable niche. The fusoms, thus provided by Shilajit, remain stable for a long period of time unless actively interacted by extraneous agents.

Fig. 1. ¹H NMR spectrum (aromatic region) of DCPs.

DCP-Supramolecular assemblies: The DCPs, isolated from the meteorites, ammonites and Shilajit (Scheme 1), exhibited HPLC chromatogram and PDA spectral patterns, and IR spectra very similar to those of each other. The major constituents detected in this extractive-fraction were metallo-proteins of the lipocalin type (protamine/histone-containing)⁵, lipids, and DBPs; the minor constituents comprised of fullerene-DBP conjugates. The ¹H NMR spectrum of the comparatively low-Mw (≤ 4 KD) DCPs, in CD₃OD, showed proton signals (Fig. 1), in the aromatic region, characteristic of oligomeric DBPs (with hydrophobic substituents/acyl-DBPs). These moieties constituted the core nuclei of the prosthetic groups of DCPs. Some of the other constituents identified in the DCPs were carotenoids (astaxanthin and equivalents), indigoids (e.g. indirubin), and the C₆₀-fullerene-DBP endo-/

DBPs, Dotted line substituted
Str. 2. Dibenzo- α -pyrone chromoproteins (DCPs).

exohedral complex. The last-named compound was isolated from the DCPs, by exhaustive extraction with toluene-ethylacetate, as a pinkish-black powder. The ESR pattern of this complex, several lines with multiple splitting, suggested the presence of metal ions in the exohedral region. The corresponding endohedral complex, a dull-yellow powder, obtained after removing the exohedral

Fig. 2. Supramolecular assemblies (MLVs) of Shilajit-DCPs.

R¹ = H/polypeptidyl
 R² = DBP-Fullerene
 X = mineralosilicates/carbonates

Str. 3. DBP-fullerene conjugates as Si-complex in meteorites, ammonites and Shilajit.

moiety with polar solvents, showed, in its ESR spectrum, a very narrow single line, without splitting, characteristic of fullerene-DBP-semiquinone donor-acceptor complex. The mixture of constituents in the DCP-assembly were disentangled by lobar chromatography on Sephadex G-25-gel. Three broad groups of DCPs were obtained. These were DCPs with \bar{M}_n range of : (i) ≥ 14 KD; (ii) 5–8 KD; and (iii) ≤ 4 KD. Re-chromatography of (iii) on Sephadex G-10, followed by SDS-PAGE operation afforded two distinct DCPs, viz., DCP-I (orange-red, more polar compound) and DCP-II (yellow, less polar compound). When DCP-I was treated with lecithins with different levels of unsaturation and with the fullerene-DBP endohedral complex, an SUV (15–25 nm) assembly was obtained. It was characterized by HPLC, IR, TEM analyses. Hence, the mixtures of DCPs, with a large array of constituents, are projected to have the chemical architecture (Str. 2) and the supramolecular assembly-form (Fig. 2).

Selective degradation of the relatively low M_w range (≤ 4 KD) DCPs lent support to the above assignments. Thus, lipase degradation followed by HPLC and GC analysis of the degraded/released products, using markers, identified, in addition to fullerene and DBPs, several colour constituents, e.g. astaxanthin, indirubin (and polymers thereof). Among the fatty acids, C₁₄ to C₂₄ acids were prominent; besides these, EPA and DHA (the precursors of DBPs) were detected among the lipase degradation products. Among the metal ions, Fe, Cu and Zn (in decreasing order of abundance) were identified.

Cationic organo-silicon compounds in HMs and HAs : The assemblies in HMs and HAs (Scheme 1) would seem to be generated from more energetic linkages of the cationic organo-silicon compounds (Str. 3). The occurrence of such silicon compounds in meteorites has

recently been reported¹. The co-occurrence of these complexes also in ammonites and in Shilajit has now been established. Purification of the constituents of HMs-HAs over Dowex-50 (H⁺) resin, followed by treatment of the eluted products with HCl-HF and the usual work-up released the individual constituents associated with the assembly (Str. 3).

Fusoms containing fullerene-DBP conjugates in systemic delivery of chemical/medicinal agents : Another object of this study was to determine the efficiency of fusoms, with or without the fullerene-DBP conjugates, in systemic delivery of chemical/medicinal agents to elicit receptor responses. It was observed that when fusoms were devoid of fullerene-DBP conjugates (magic bullets) in their micropores, they were much less efficient as the carrier system than when impregnated with the "magic bullets". Likewise, the DCP-assemblies (Fig. 2), when impregnated with the fullerene-DBP conjugates (L in Str 1) were more efficient as drug delivery system than when devoid of (L). The concentration of fullerene-DBP conjugates in the fusoms and DCPs, isolated from good quality Shilajit, ranged from 0.1–0.3% w/w. The contents of fullerene-DBP conjugates are much higher (0.5–0.8%) in the extractives of certain genera of ammonites. In poor quality Shilajit the fullerene-DBP conjugates were either not detected, or were present in traces.

The fullerene-DBP impregnated fusoms (Str. 1) and DCPs (Str. 2, Fig. 2), in aqueous solutions, conferred solubility, stability, and superior bioavailability to a host of natural and synthetic agents, e.g. vitamins, steroids, toxic anticancer drugs (e.g. doxorubicin), and insulin (biodegradable when administered through the oral route), that are ordinarily either water-insoluble, thermolabile, autoxidizable or prematurely biodegradable before reaching the target site.

The versatility of the fullerene-DBP "magic bullet" – impregnated fusoms and DCPs, from Shilajit, as efficient drug delivery system (*Yogabahi* in Ayurveda) was tested in the present study with different classes of pharmaceutical and therapeutic agents. A few examples are cited here.

Doxorubicin, a toxic but potent anthracyclin anti-cancer drug, in human malignancies, suffers from a major deficiency that it accumulates preferentially in the heart and thus produces overt cardiac toxicity. To make it tumour target oriented, liposomal delivery of doxorubicin was attempted^{14,15}, without much success. In the present

study, we observed that fusom, impregnated with the fullerene-DBP conjugates (endo-/exohedral complexes), significantly reduced both the dose and toxicity of doxorubicin while targeting EAC (Ehrlich Ascitic Carcinoma) tumours in mice. Variable extents of anti-tumour effects of fusom-doxorubicin formulations, with or without the fullerene-DBP conjugates, vis-à-vis the tumour-control group of animals were observed. The effects were evaluated on the basis of body weight, tumour-volume, survival period, non-viable cell count, and the health status of the animals during the experimental period. The results are incorporated in Table 1. In all of these parameters, fusom-doxorubicin formulation containing (i) fullerene-DBP as the magic bullet within the fusom micropores, (5 : 1, w/w) (in doses of 1 mg/kg day⁻¹), elicited superior therapeutic potential/efficacy compared to those of the (ii) doxorubicin (2 mg/kg day⁻¹) group. Furthermore, the fusom formulation, without the fullerene-DBP conjugates, exhibited much weaker bioactivity compared to that of group (i) (vide Experimental). Additionally, the overt toxic symptoms exhibited by the animals of the group (ii), due to higher dose of doxorubicin, were not found in the animals of group (i). These were manifested by the gait, skin and hair texture, food and water intake by the tumour-bearing animals. The conditions of the internal organs, e.g. heart, spleen, kidneys and liver, of the treated animals also were much better in group (i) compared to those of group (ii). Thus, superior chemotherapeutic effect was observed in the fullerene-DBP conjugate-impregnated fusom-doxorubicin treated group, compared to those of the doxorubicin alone (even in higher dose) – or of the fusom doxorubicin without fullerene-DBP conjugate, treated

group. It is conjectured that, if the percentage of fullerene-DBP conjugates can be enriched (higher than the normally occurring 0.1–0.3%) in fusoms (occurring to the extent of 40–60%) and in DCPs (10–18%) in pure, water-soluble Shilajit, then the therapeutic index will be improved considerably.

Yet another significant observation of the fusoms with fullerene-DBP conjugates as the drug delivery system, was their consistent effect to responses of an oral insulin formulation in STZ-induced diabetic rats. In an earlier invention⁶, what was provided as a possible drug delivery system for oral insulin was a purified Shilajit composition containing about 40% by weight of fulvic acids (FAs), with internal voids, substantially free of any chemical constituent (in the micropores). Use of this formulation⁶, containing insulin, in the present study, showed inconsistent results. This is presumably, because of the fact, that, mechanical mixing of insulin with FAs in Shilajit, containing unevenly dispersed/with sparsely present fullerene-DBP conjugates would not provide consistent responses. The formulation must contain the magic bullet (fullerene-DBP conjugates), appropriately stuffed with insulin, within the fusoms micropores. Similar magic bullet effect of fullerene-DBP conjugates, when stuffed-in with insulin, was observed in case of a DCP formulation. By contrast, when the DCP-core was free of fullerene-DBP conjugates, the corresponding insulin formulation elicited only feeble effect (p.o.). Most significantly, even without the addition of exogenous insulin to DCPs, with fullerene-DBP conjugates, it acted as an efficient insulin-delivery system of the low-level of insulin endogenously secreted by the STZ-diabetic animals. As fullerene (and equivalents) are avid acceptors of electron and the electron transfer

Table 1. Anti-tumour effect of fusom-doxorubicin in mice

Groups	Body wt (g)	Tumour volume (ml)	Mean days of survival	Non-viable cells (%)
1 Saline-control	34 ± 07	–	>42	–
2 EAC-control	41 ± 09	3.3 ± 0.20	14.02	8.8
3 Fusom-doxorubicin with F-D (1 mg/kg)	34 ± 03	0.23 ± 0.01	28 ± 09	55.2
4 Fusom-doxorubicin without F-D (1 mg/kg)	37 ± 09	0.44 ± 0.07	23 ± 04	48.1
5 Doxorubicin (2 mg/kg)	19 ± 03	0.36 ± 0.03	21 ± 08	45.3

Values are mean of six replicates, –, indicates absent, F-D, fullerene-DBP complex

Note the pronounced effect of the group 3 formulation (fusom-doxorubicin with fullerene-DBP complex) even when administered at half the dose of doxorubicin

ability of hydroxy-DBPs to produce semiquinone radical is well known⁵, this could be one of the most important applications of the fullerene-DBP conjugates to adduct formation with insulin and its safe delivery to the target site. In case of a mechanical mixture⁶ of insulin and Shilajit-FAs (perhaps without the fullerene-DBP conjugates), such adduct formation with insulin not being possible, the concentration of systemic insulin is elevated. Consequently, tissue sensitivity to insulin is further reduced. This would result in adverse clinical signs of (false) relative insulin-deficit, e.g. polydipsia and polyuria in the treated animals. By contrast, insulin, on prior adduct formation with the fullerene-DBP conjugates (L in Str. 1), followed by its incorporation into the carrier (fusoms or DCPs) would provide formulations that would elicit consistent anti-hyperglycemic effect in diabetic animals. The details of this proposal is now being worked out in our laboratories. Such "magic bullet" character of fullerenes has precedent in the literature^{16,17}.

Key to abbreviations :

C-T complex, charge-transfer complex; DBP, dibenzo- α -pyrone; DCP, dibenzo- α -pyrone chromo protein; DHA, docosahexaenoic acid; EPA, eicosa-pentaenoic acid; ESR, electron spin resonance; FAs, fulvic acids; HAs, humic acids; HMs, humins; MLVs, multilamellar vesicles; \bar{M}_n , number average mol. wt.; PAGE, polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis; PBQ, polyphenyl benzoquinone; STZ, Streptozotocin; SUVs, small unilamellar vesicles; TEM, transmission electron microscopy.

Experimental

Test samples : The meteorite samples were obtained from Messers Impactika, Denver, Colorado, USA, and the authentication certificate was obtained in each case¹. The ammonite samples⁵ were obtained from the Geological Survey of India, Kolkata, and Geological Science Museum, Jadavpur University, Kolkata (through the courtesy of Prof. S. Bardhan). Shilajit (native) samples were collected⁵ from the Kumaon region of the Himalayas (through the courtesy of the CCRAS, Almorah). Specimens of all these samples have been preserved.

Treatment-A : In a typical experiment, the FAs-fusoms (Scheme 1) was dissolved in water and the yellowish-brown solution was passed through a column of Sephadex G-10. The column was eluted with water. Ten fractions were collected. Three middle fractions (4–6) were combined, being similar in their HPTLC patterns, and extracted with toluene-ethylacetate (93 : 7). Evaporation of the solvent gave a black residue which was lightly washed with hexane to remove adherent impurities and fatty matter.

(C₆₀)-Fullerene-3,8-(OH)₂-DBP endo-/exohedral complex (L in Str. 1) : The hexane-insoluble residue was obtained as a pinkish-black powder; HPTLC [CAMAG assembly; detection, quenching mode, λ 260 nm; developer, toluene-ethyl acetate (99 : 1)] showed two major components : R_F 0.25, reflectance λ_{\max} 218, 232, 252, 272, 300, 350 nm; and R_F 0.70, λ_{\max} 218, 262, 333, 365, 390, 408, 428, 495, 562, 620 nm. Prep. TLC-scrappings around R_F 0.3, followed by usual work-up, afforded a greenish-yellow powder; FT-IR (JASCO 5300 spectrometer) : γ_{\max} (KBr) 3380, 3260, 1762, 1728, 1700, 1620, 1120 cm⁻¹, typical of oxygenated dibenzo- α -pyrones⁵; EI-MS : *m/z* 454 (M⁺, 100), 426, 425, 398, 340, the M⁺ and fragment ion peaks were indistinguishable from those of 3,3',8,8'-tetrahydroxy-9,9'-bis-dibenzo- α -pyrone¹². The second major component, a pinkish-black solid obtained from the prep. TLC scrapings around R_F 0.7, exhibited, in HPTLC, reflectance maxima : λ_{\max} 212, 218, 234, 262, 332, 390, 408, 430, 535, 562, 590, 620 nm; FAB-MS (JMS-AX 505H), using *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol as a matrix; *m/z* 940 (C₆₀-fullerene-3,8-(OH)₂-DBP endohedral adduct), 720 (C₆₀-fullerene), 454 (3,3',8,8'-tetrahydroxy-9,9'-bis-dibenzo- α -pyrone¹²); EI-MS *m/z* 454 (M⁺), 453 (semiquinone radical of bis-DBP), 228 (M⁺ of 3,8-(OH)₂-DBP), 227 (semiquinone radical of 3,8-(OH)₂-DBP). The pinkish-black solid (hexane-insoluble) in its ESR spectrum (Varian E-112; room temp.; modulation frequency, 100 KHz; microwave frequency, ca. 9.5 GHz) exhibited an eight line spectrum, with multiple splitting due to metal ions in the fullerene-DBP endo-/exohedral complex. The solid was washed with toluene-methylene chloride to remove the fullerene-DBP-metal ion exohedral complex as insoluble residue; the toluene-methylene chloride soluble part, on removal of the solvent, yielded fullerene-DBP endohedral complex as a dull-yellow powder, UV : λ_{\max} (toluene) 218, 230, 260, 276, 330, 428, 460 nm; EI-MS : *m/z* 720 (M⁺, C₆₀-fullerene), 454 (bis-DBP), 452 (hemiquinone of bis-DBP), 228 (3,8-(OH)₂-DBP), 227 (semiquinone of 3,8-(OH)₂-DBP); ESR : very narrow single line, devoid of hyperfine splitting with *g*-value ranging from 1.99–2.001 (for the endohedral complexes obtained from the FAs-fusoms from the three different sources; – meteorites, ammonites, and Shilajit). The absence of free fullerene and free DBPs in the endohedral complex was established by HPTLC, using markers.

Synthesis of fullerene-DBP endo-/exohedral complex : Fullerene soot (MER Corp., Tucson, Az) was refluxed with nitric acid, to open up the terminal blockades of the

fullerene nano tubes, according to a published procedure¹⁶. The product (18 mg) was suspended in toluene-methylene chloride to which 3,8-(OAc)₂-DBP (54 mg) and catalytic amount of FeCl₃ were added. The mixture was stirred for 24 h, then heated in a thick-wall Erlenmeyer flask, stoppered with a screw-cap, under N₂ atmosphere (temp. ca. 100 °C, 2 h). After evaporation of the solvent, the residue was dissolved in tetrahydrofuran, containing catalytic amount of ferric chloride. The solution was evaporated to give a black residue. The chromatographic (HPTLC) and spectroscopic properties : λ_{\max} (toluene) 218, 232, 262, 276, 318, 334, 408, 430, 455 nm; and γ_{\max} (KBr) 3384, 3256, 1760, 1725, 1598, 1130 cm⁻¹, were very similar to those of the natural fullerene-DBP endo-/exohedral complex (L in Str. 1).

Fusoms : The aqueous mother liquor, left after toluene-ethylacetate (93 : 7) extraction (treatment-A) was passed through a column of Dowex-50 (H⁺) resin. Evaporation of the eluted fraction gave fusoms (with voids) as a yellowish-brown powder. Its transmission electron micrograph showed a sponge-like structure of variable thickness, punctured by voids, which are capable of nesting several fullerene nanotubes (2–5 nm in diam.) stuffed with DBPs. Re-entry of the fullerene-DBP endo-/exohedral complex into the voids of fusoms was accomplished. Trituration of the fusom solution in citrate buffer (pH ~5.0), with the pinkish-black solid produced the supramolecular assembly (MLVs), capable of incorporating many pharmaceutical and therapeutic agents, via the fullerene-DBP magic bullets, into systemic receptors.

Treatment-B : The mixture of DCPs (Scheme 1), isolated from the three sources, exhibited very similar HPLC patterns in the t_R range 1.2-1.5 min; λ_{\max} (PDA) 212, 220, ~232, 262, 270, 282, ~295, 325, 348, 372, 408, 432, ~490, 555 nm; contributed by C₆₀-fullerene-3,8-(OH)₂-DBP chromophores. The ¹H NMR spectrum of the DCPs, in CD₃OD, showed signals in the aromatic region (δ 6.9–8.5 ppm) (Fig. 1) characteristic of oligomeric DBP-protons. The DCPs were separated by lobar chromatography (Biologic-LP, Biorad, USA) on Sephadex G-25 column (22 × 1.5 cm); using Tris buffer (pH 8.0); flow rate, 2 ml/min; injected volume, 1.5 ml, consisting of DCPs (10 mg/ml). Five fractions (1–5) were collected. Fractions-1 and -2 yielded high mol. wt. (>14 KD) DCPs; fractions-3 and -4, gave medium mol. wt. (5–8 KD) DCPs, and fraction-5 yielded low mol. wt. (\leq 4 KD) DCPs.

Repeated extraction of this last DCP-fraction with toluene-ethylacetate, followed by usual work-up, afforded the fullerene-DBP endo-/exohedral complex (L in Str. 1). Re-chromatography of fraction-5-DCP over Sephadex G-10 column resulted in further separation of the DCPs. Finally, application of SDS-PAGE (110 V, 30 mA, 90 min, 15 °C) provided DCP-I, orange-red; and DCP-II, yellow (less polar), with weak conductivities. DCP-I and -II were subjected to HPLC analysis [C₁₈-Novapak RP-18 column, 150 mm × 3.9 mm; using acetonitrile-water-phosphoric acid, 32 : 67 : 1 as the mobile phase; waters 2996 PDA detector, flow rate 0.6 ml/min] when the t_R and PDA spectral positions showed the presence of fullerene-DBP conjugates in both these DCPs.

Treatment-C : HMs and HAs, obtained from each of the three sources (Scheme 1), were combined and stirred with an aqueous solution of conc. HCl (0.5%) and 48% HF (0.5%). The extract was filtered and then passed through Dowex-50 (H⁺)-resin. The eluted fraction was divided into two parts (i and ii). Part (i) was extracted with *n*-butanol and part (ii) was dialysed. Part (i) gave a reddish-brown residue from the *n*-butanol extract. In part (ii) the salts and low-to-medium mol. wt. compounds were separated by dialysis. In another set of experiment (iii), the products, after HCl-HF treatment, were passed through Amberlite IRA-400 (Cl⁻). The eluates were combined and evaporated under N₂. The reddish-brown residue, that resulted from each of the above experiments (i to iii) was found to contain fullerene-DBP endo-/exohedral complexes. The identities of these products were established by HPTLC and IR spectra as before.

Biological procedures :

The biological experiments with the isolated products were carried out by following standard procedures as described earlier^{6,18,19}. Briefly, the anti-cancer effect of fusom (with or without fullerene-DBP conjugates)-doxorubicin (5 : 1, w/w, 1 mg/kg b.w., day⁻¹ for 12 days) was evaluated by administering (through oral route, p.o.) the formulations to EAC-bearing mice. Doxorubicin itself (2 mg/kg day⁻¹) was administered for comparison purpose. The results are incorporated in Table 1.

In the anti-diabetic screening, the regimen and treatment in male rats (Sprague-Dawley Strain, 150 ± 20 g) consisted of administering STZ, dissolved in 0.1 *N* citrate buffer (50 mg/kg b.w., intraperitoneal, i.p.) to produce diabetic conditions. DCPs (cavitand-packed with

fullerene-DBP conjugates) were administered (50 mg/kg b.w., day⁻¹, p.o. for 21 days). In another set of experiment DCPs (50 mg/kg), admixed with insulin (2.5 IU/kg) was administered in the same way and for the same period of time. For comparison purpose, insulin (8 IU/kg, s.c.) and glibenclamide (0.42 mg/kg, dissolved in water, p.o.) were administered to two other groups of rats. DCPs, cavitand-packed with fullerene-DBP conjugates, without addition of insulin, when administered orally, the blood glucose level in diabetic rats was appreciably reduced (125 mg/dl), compared to that of the untreated rats (281 mg/dl). The standard drugs, viz. insulin and glibenclamide, as expected, brought down the blood glucose levels of the treated rats to 96 and 98 mg/dl, respectively. However, administration of DCP-insulin mixture (containing 50 mg/kg DCP and 2.5 IU/kg insulin) elicited inconsistent responses in respect of lowering of the blood-glucose level. In yet another set of experiment, insulin was interacted (sonication and heating) with fullerene-DBP endo-/exohedral complex, containing transition metal ions, in tetrahydrofuran; the solvent was removed by chasing with N₂. The final concentration of the components in the composite formulation was : DCP (50 mg/kg), containing fullerene-DBP complex (1 mg/kg)-cavitand packed with insulin (0.25 IU/kg). This formulation when administered to diabetic rats brought down the blood glucose level to 95 mg/dl. The details of these findings will be reported elsewhere.

Acknowledgement

We very much appreciate the technical assistance provided to us, during this investigation, by the Scientists of the Chemistry and Pharmacology Sections of the R&D Centre, Indian Herbs, Saharanpur.

References

1. S. Ghosal, *Science & Culture*, 2008, **74**, 22.
2. M. A. Sephton, *Nat. Prod. Rep.*, 2002, **19**, 292.
3. J. Pojeta (Jr.) in "Fossil Invertebrates", eds. R. S. Boargman, A. H. Cheetham and A. J. Rowwell, Blackwell, NJ, p. 270.
4. S. Ghosal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 930; *Proc.* (Keynote address) : Interactive Seminar on Ayurvedic *Rasausadhi*, Central Research Institute (Ay), Kolkata, 30 May, 2008.
5. S. Ghosal in "Shilajit in perspective", Narosa-Alpha Science Internl., New Delhi/Oxford, 2006, Chap. 3.
6. S. Ghosal, US patent, 2002, 6440436; 2003, 6558712 B1; 2005, 6869612.
7. A. S. Webster, *Nature*, 1991, **352**, 412.
8. O. Ermer, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1991, **74**, 1339; G. X. Dona and J. S. L., *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1994, 1725.
9. L. Becker, J. L. Bada, R. E. Williams and T. E. Bunch, *Nature*, 1994, **372**, 507.
10. S. Pizzarillo, Y. Huang, L. Becker and M. Williams, *Sci. Exp.*, 2001, **293**, 2236.
11. F. J. M. Rietmeijer, in "Developments in Fullerene Science", Vol. 6, Springer, Netherlands, 2006, pp. 123-144.
12. S. Ghosal, J. Lal, R. Kanth and Y. Kumar, *Soil Biol. Biochem.*, 1993, **25**, 377.
13. M. Schnitzer in "Soil Organic Matter", eds. M. Schnitzer and A. U. Khan, Elsevier, NY, pp. 1-58.
14. E. A. Fossen and Z. A. Tokes, *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.*, 1979, **91**, 1295.
15. R. Krishna and L. D. Mayer, *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2000, **11**, 265.
16. S. C. Tsang, Y. K. Chen, P. J. F. Harris and A. H. Green, *Nature*, 1994, **372**, 159.
17. N. Tagmatarchis and H. Shinohara, *Mol. Rev. Med. Chem.*, 2001, **1**, 339.
18. S. Ghosal, B. Mukhopadhyay and S. K. Bhattacharya, in "Molecular Aspects of Asian Medicines", eds. A. Mori and T. Satoh, PJD Pub., NY, Vol. 1, 2000, Chap. XI, p. 425.
19. U. Chattopadhyay, S. Das, S. Guha, and S. Ghosal, *Cancer Letts.*, 1987, **37**, 293.